

Research Article

Air Quality Assessment in Petaling Jaya Using Principal Component Analysis

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Abstract: Air pollution, a major environmental concern, negatively affects human health and the environment. In Malaysia, urban areas such as Petaling Jaya (PJ) in Selangor have suffered from increased air pollution due to heavy industrial activities, dense populations, and high vehicular traffic, which are particularly vulnerable. This study identified Selangor's air quality trends using the Department of Environment (DOE) data. The monitoring station in PJ was selected based on six air pollutants (sulphur dioxide (SO₂), particulate matter below 10 microns (PM₁₀), ozone (O₃), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), carbon monoxide (CO) and particulate matter below 2.5 microns (PM_{2.5}) during three years from January 1, 2020, to December 31, 2022. This study aims to use the principal component analysis (PCA) method to classify the variables that predict the air pollution index (API) in PJ, Selangor. PCA was used to reduce dimensionality and identify significant pollutant predictors, with Bartlett's test and KMO measure supporting data suitability and rotating PCA by reducing predictor variables. As a result, two principal components that highlighted PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and O₃ as the most important pollutants in PJ were revealed after the PCA was rotated using varimax rotation. The finding could assist DOE management in identifying the types of pollutants responsible for air pollution.

Keywords: Air Pollution Index; principal component analysis; Petaling Jaya.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The issue of air pollution is not new to any country worldwide, including Malaysia which is one of the most serious environmental issues facing the world today. There are plenty of different types of pollution, including noise, ground, water, and air pollution. Air pollution refers to the contamination of the atmosphere by another harmful substance. Air pollution is the contamination of the indoor or outdoor environment by any chemical, physical or biological agent that modifies the natural characteristics of the atmosphere (World Health Organization, 2023). After considering the information regarding air pollution, it is not only dangerous for human health but also makes it unsuitable for people to live in if air pollution continues to increase in the future.

Motor vehicles, power plants, and industry as major sources of air pollution in Malaysia (Ku Yusof et al., 2019). Industrial smoke, cigarette smoke, open burning, and household combustion devices

contribute to air pollution. Moreover, Astro Awani (2024) said that urban areas in Malaysia have the highest levels of PM₁₀, a harmful inhalable particle, and higher levels of (O₃), a secondary air pollutant produced by industrial emissions and motor vehicle exhausts. Malaysia has also seen an increase in carbon monoxide (CO) emissions due to fossil fuel reliance.

The US Environmental Protection Agency’s Air Quality measure (AQI) is the most extensively used global air quality measure, adopted by many countries, including Malaysia (Mohamed et al., 2016). Based on research from Maleki et al. (2019) said that the United States Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA) provides daily air quality conditions using six criteria: sulphur dioxide (SO₂), particulate matter below 10 microns (PM₁₀), ozone (O₃), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), carbon monoxide (CO) and particulate matter below 2.5 microns (PM_{2.5}). Each pollutant has unique effects on human health, with sulphur dioxide SO₂ causing asthma, particulate matter below 10 microns PM₁₀ causing lung cancer, ozone O₃ causing breathing problems, nitrogen dioxide NO₂ related to asthma and other respiratory diseases, and carbon monoxide (CO) causing breathing difficulties, exhaustion, dizziness, and flu-like symptoms. Particulate matter below 2.5 microns PM_{2.5} can also cause cardiovascular, cerebrovascular, and respiratory effects. The index value set is classified as good, moderate, unhealthy, very unhealthy, hazardous, or emergency, indicating the air quality’s potential harm to humans and the environment, as indicated in Table 1.

Table 1. Air Pollutant Index (API) of Malaysia

Air Pollution Index	Air Pollution Level
0 to 50	Good
51 to 100	Moderate
101 to 200	Unhealthy
201 to 300	Very Unhealthy
> 300	Hazardous
>500	Emergency

Seven million premature deaths annually are caused by air pollution (World Health Organization, 2023). Malaysia’s Ministry of Health reports that respiratory system diseases cause 10.36% of deaths, with 19.48% due to these diseases. Accurate prediction of API is essential for implementing timely interventions, informed decision-making, and effective air quality management. However, identifying a robust model that balances accuracy, computational efficiency, and interpretability remains a challenge. This study aims to bridge this gap by leveraging Principal Component Analysis (PCA) for dimensionality reduction. By applying these advanced techniques, the research seeks to develop an optimized model for predicting API in Petaling Jaya contributing to better air quality management and public health outcomes.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Data Description

The study used secondary data from the Department of Environment’s Malaysia air pollution index, covering the period from January 1, 2020 to December 31, 2022. The index was calculated using daily observations from the Petaling Jaya air quality monitoring stations. Pollutants included sulphur dioxide (SO₂), particulate matter below 10 microns (PM₁₀), ozone (O₃), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), carbon monoxide (CO) and particulate matter below 2.5 microns (PM_{2.5}).

2.2 Dimensionality Reduction

Principal component analysis (PCA) was a multivariate statistical method that combined information gathered from many different variables observed on the same individuals into a smaller number of variables known as principal components (PCs) (Greenacre et al., 2022). According to Hasan & Abdulazeez (2021), PCA was a dimensionality reduction (DR) technique that commonly utilised to reduce a large number of variables into a smaller number that still maintained some of the details in the large set. The PCA was performed to obtain principal components (PCs). The PCs could be expressed as

$$z_{ij} = \alpha_i1x_{1j} + \alpha_i2x_{2j} + \alpha_i3x_{3j} + \alpha_i4x_{4j} + \alpha_i5x_{5j} + \alpha_i6x_{6j} \tag{1}$$

- where
- z is the component score
 - α is the component loading
 - x_1 is sulphur dioxide (SO₂)
 - x_2 is particulate matter below 10 microns (PM₁₀)
 - x_3 is ozone (O₃)
 - x_4 is nitrogen dioxide (NO₂)
 - x_5 is carbon monoxide (CO)
 - x_6 particulate matter below 2.5 microns (PM_{2.5})
 - i is component number
 - j is the sample number

The correlation of variables in a PCA was evaluated using Bartlett’s test of sphericity. The null hypothesis (H₀) suggested the original correlation matrix was an identity matrix, indicating unrelated variables. The alternative hypothesis (H₁) suggested the correlation matrix was significantly different from the identity matrix. A significant result (p-value < 0.05) indicated that factor analysis might be useful for the data set (Shrestha, 2021). According to Mahmud et al. (2021), this approach was used to describe the variability of a large group of connected variables and a smaller set of uncorrelated variables known as principal components. The KMO test was a measure designed to determine the suitability of data for factor analysis, measuring the adequacy of sample size. The test examined the sampling adequacy for each variable in the model and the whole model. KMO values below 0.6 indicated inadequate sampling and required corrective action (Shrestha, 2021).

Varimax rotation is a method used to reduce component complexity in PCs generated by the PCA, simplifying and improving the examination of variable structure. It involves raising high loads while decreasing small loads. PCs with eigenvalues greater than one were used to construct new variables, such as varimax factors (VFs) or factor loads, specifically in the varimax rotation process (Mahmud et al., 2021). The Kaiser Criterion addresses maintain the required number of components. Varimax rotations require several variables aligned with conventional criteria, including non-observable, theoretical, and latent variables. Varimax factors (VFs) were the values used to calculate the correlation between variables. The values of varimax factors (VFs) could be categorised into three groups as shown in Table 2. The selection standard for this analysis is determined for VFs with absolute values over 0.75.

Table 2. Category of varimax factor values

Varimax Factor Values	Category
> 0.75	Strong
0.50 ≥ VF ≥ 0.75	Moderate
0.30 ≥ VF ≥ 0.49	Weak

3. FINDINGS

After analyzing the data using IBM SPSS Statistics, the result revealed which pollutants were significant for determining the air pollution index for Petaling Jaya. Table 3 presents the results of Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett’s sphericity tests.

Table 3. KMO and Bartlett’s Test for Petaling Jaya

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		0.621
Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	3037.211
	df	15
	Sig.	0.000

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test for Petaling Jaya data showed that the sampling adequacy was greater than 0.6, suggesting that all variables were suitable for further analysis. Factor loading calculations were conducted to evaluate the relationships between variables and extracted factors. Aside from that, Bartlett’s test of sphericity displayed that the air pollution index data met the sphericity requirement, as the p-value was 0.000, which is less than 0.05. Consequently, the variables were determined to be connected rather than orthogonal. This indicated that PCA enabled the interpretation of data variability with less variables than the original number of variables.

Table 4 shows the results after applying varimax rotation. The number of principal components (PCs) to be retained was determined by examining the value of eigenvalues greater than one from the initial eigenvalues, which listed the six variables. According to Shrestha (2021), the retained components should account for at least 50% of the total variance, as recommended.

Table 4. Summary of Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variances	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variances	Cumulative %
1	2.541	42.356	42.356	2.361	39.349	39.349
2	1.430	23.834	66.190	1.610	26.841	66.190
3	0.883	14.715	80.905			
4	0.657	10.946	91.850			
5	0.419	6.979	98.829			
6	0.070	1.171	100.00			

As a result, Table 4 reveals that only two out of six principal components (PCs) were selected for Petaling Jaya, as the eigenvalues were greater than one, accounting for 66.190% of the total variance in the data. The study selected PC1 and PC2 for Petaling Jaya due to their eigenvalues exceeding one, allowing for the creation of new variables known as varimax factors (VFs). VF values greater than 0.75 were chosen as a criterion for this study since it falls in the strong category, indicating moderate to significant highlights on eliminated components. Table 5 showed that three out of six air pollutants met the 0.75 VF threshold, with PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and O₃ being the most significant contributors.

Table 5. Rotated Component Matrix

	Component	
	1	2
PM₁₀	0.954	
PM_{2.5}	0.951	
NO ₂	0.647	-0.516
O ₃		0.753
CO	0.295	-0.688
SO ₂	0.198	0.547

After rotation, Component 1 accounted for approximately 39.349% of the variation in air quality data as shown in Table 4. Based on the varimax factor (VF) value categories outlined in methodology, Table 5, two pollutants with absolute VF values exceeding 0.75 have a strong VF value, which is PM₁₀ (0.954) and PM_{2.5} (0.951). According to Sentian et al., (2018), particulate matter (PM), also known as dust or aerosols, is primarily caused by road traffic, construction, mining operations, wind erosion, agricultural activities, southwest monsoon wind, and burning biomass during the dry season in Malaysia.

Component 2, as shown in Table 4, contributes about 26.481% of the variability in air quality data. For this component, there is only one pollutant that contained absolute values of VF that exceeded than 0.75: O₃ (0.753). According to Hashim et al., (2019), the rapid growth of industries and human activities in the ground-level atmosphere leads to increased levels of nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and volatile organic compounds (VOC), precursors to ozone. Due to the direct release of numerous pollutants, such as carbon monoxide (CO), volatile organic compounds (VOC), and nitrogen oxides (NO_x, a mixture that consist of both NO and NO₂), motor vehicles are an important cause of air pollution, health concerns for the public, and problems connected to the changing global climate (Sahrir et al., 2019).

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the primary air contaminants in Petaling Jaya may be determined using principal component analysis (PCA). The data on air pollution satisfied the sphericity assumption of Bartlett's test, with a p-value of less than 0.05, indicating that the variables associated with air pollution were correlated rather than orthogonal. By using the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test, it was determined that all pollutants considered worthy of further investigation were acceptable and that the sampling adequacy was higher than 0.6. Two different PCs produced by rotating the PCA with varimax rotation showed that three out of six pollutants are the most significant pollutants in Petaling Jaya, with the selected pollutants namely PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and O₃.

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